

A REVIEW ON SIRA NIDANA IN NETRA ROGA: AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE ON VASCULAR ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF OCULAR DISORDERS AND MANAGEMENT**Dr. Swapnil Pandharinath Gunjal*¹, Dr. Pratik Pandurang Gaikwad², Dr. Archana Kanase Patil³**¹Associate Professor, Shalakyatantra Dept., Bhimashankar Ayurved College, Vadgaon Kashimbeg Manchar, Pune (Maharashtra) India.²Associate Professor, Rognidan and Vikriti Vigyana Dept., Bhimashankar Ayurved College, Vadgaon Kashimbeg Manchar, Pune (Maharashtra) India.³Assistant Professor, Rognidan and Vikriti Vigyana Dept., Bhimashankar Ayurved College, Vadgaon Kashimbeg Manchar, Pune (Maharashtra) India.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Swapnil Pandharinath Gunjal**Associate Professor, Shalakyatantra Dept., Bhimashankar Ayurved College, Vadgaon Kashimbeg Manchar, Pune (Maharashtra) India. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20022819>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Swapnil Pandharinath Gunjal*¹, Dr. Pratik Pandurang Gaikwad², Dr. Archana Kanase Patil³. (2026). A Review on Sira Nidana In Netra Roga: Ayurvedic Perspective on Vascular Etiopathogenesis of Ocular Disorders and Management. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(5), 376–378.

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ABSTRACT

According to the principles of Ayurveda, there are two aspects that form the basis of Ayurvedic diagnosis and treatment that are known as *Roga Pariksha* and *Rogi Pariksha*. *Roga Pariksha* carries the diagnosis of a disease from a broad etiologic perspective to its completed manifestation. The five main elements that constitute *Roga Pariksha* are *Nidana*, *Purvarupa*, *Rupa*, *Samprapti* and *Upashaya*. The central component of *Nidana* is the identification of the causative factors and is also very important in that it provides a basis for the avoidance of those factors through appropriate management. *Netra* is the most *Pradhana* of all the *Indriyas* and therefore it requires great caution to protect it. Understanding of the causative factors that lead to eyes diseases is essential in order to plan the appropriate treatment for the preservation of *Netra Roga*.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, Netra Roga, Nidana, Ocular Disorders, Etiopathogenesis.***INTRODUCTION**

The eye or the *Netra* is one of the most complex and important organs in the human body. Ayurveda believes that when the *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha Doshas* are in their balanced state, the physiological functions of the body are normal. When these *Doshas* become vitiated, manifestations of disease can occur, including *Netra Rogas*. The *Nidanas* of eye disorders described in the classical Ayurvedic literature are very important in understanding both the cause and the development of eye diseases and disorders that already exist and the emergence of new ones. From a clinical perspective, the *Nidanas* of *Netra Rogas* can be grouped into different categories which includes; *Aharaja*, *Viharaja*, *Ritu Viparyaya*, *Manasika*, *Agantuja*, *Bheshaja*, *Nidanarthakara* and *Sankramika Nidanas*.^[1-3]

There are many aspects to consider when looking at the eye condition from a holistic point of view. The most

common causes of eye problems are emotional factors such as grieving. Grieving affects the *Sharirika* and *Manasika dosha* are the main reason for eye problems. When someone experiences physical trauma, such as an accident or injury, they may develop a serious visual impairment, even if the original injury was of minimal consequence. Diet is another important factor that can cause vision loss. For example, consuming excessive amounts of sour foods may result in a person losing *Ojokshaya*, which is one of the primary causes of eye problems. Similarly, excessive consumption of *Kashaya Rasa* and *Katu Vipaka* foods will exacerbate the *Pitta* and *Rakta doshas*, which may lead to *Pittaja Netra Rogas* and *Raktaja Netra Rogas*, respectively. Excessive consumption of *Guru*, *Snigdha* and *Madhura* foods will also contribute to *Kaphaja* vision problems.^[4-6]

Some aspects of a person's lifestyle can also contribute to vision problems. Withholding or suppressing natural

urges creates an upward movement of energy called *Udavarta*, which may increase the pressure in the ocular structures and cause vision problems. Excessive *Swedana* treatments, particularly if directed at the eyes, can produce *Pittaja* and *Raktaja* vision problems if not performed properly. Engaging in habits such as smoking will increase the *Vata* and *Pitta doshas* and may contribute to conditions such as *Timira*.^[5-7]

Sira Nidana in Netra Roga (Vascular Etiopathogenesis of Ocular Disorders)

Sira are described as channels responsible for circulation of *Rakta* and nourishment of tissues. In the context of *Netra*, *Sira* play a crucial role in maintaining *Drishti*, *Poshana* of *Netra Dhatu* and maintaining *Dosha* balance, especially *Alochaka Pitta*. Any disturbance in these vascular channels leads to pathological changes in ocular structures. The *Sanga* and *Vimargagamana* within the *Strotas* mainly affect *Raktavaha Strotas*. Clinical signs include retinal hemorrhages and tortuosity due to the involvement of *Rakta Dhatu*. The *Ashraya-Ashrayi*

Bhava relationship exists between *Pitta* and *Rakta*, which means that correcting *Pitta* will then also correct *Rakta Dushti*.^[6-8]

The Ayurvedic perspective recognizes that the various manifestations of *Netra Rogas* arise from the concentration of vitiated *Doshas* within the *Siras* of the eye. The location of the *Netra Rogas* is determined by the state of the underlying *Pradesika Dhatu Dushti*. Affects on the function of the *Dhatwagni* and *Bhutagni* cause *Srotorodha* to the channels, hence blocking the circulation of *Pitta* and *Rakta*. These conditions would result in localized ischemia that would resemble the clinical signs of *Shanika Pandu Lakshana* and correlate with the appearance of cotton wool spots in the retinal nerve fiber layer ischemia.^[7-9] There are various *Sira Nidanans* affecting vascular integrity, leading to eye diseases as mentioned in **Table 1**. The major pathological events associated with such types of condition are depicted in **Figure 1**.

Table 1: Sira Nidanans Responsible for Vascular Etiopathogenesis of Ocular Disorders.

Category	Effect on Sira (Vascular Changes)	Related Eye Problems
<i>Dosha Prakopa</i> affecting <i>Sira</i>	Constriction, dryness, ischemia	Degeneration, visual disturbance
	Inflammation and hemorrhage	Redness, Sensation
	Stagnation and fluid accumulation	Edema, Sluggish circulation
<i>Rakta Dushti</i>	Dilatation of vessels	Vascular engorgement
	Hemorrhagic	Subconjunctival hemorrhage
	Inflammation	Conjunctivitis
External & Lifestyle Factors	Aggravates <i>Pitta</i> , vascular dilation	Burning, redness
	Mechanical irritation of <i>Sira</i>	Watering, congestion
<i>Abhighata</i>	Rupture or obstruction of vessels	Hemorrhage, ischemia and vision impairment

Figure 1: Samprapti of Sira Involvement in Netra Roga.

Management

Ayurveda has therapies for the management of common eye diseases such as *Shushkakshipaka*, *Abhishyanda*,

Klinnavartma, *Timira* and *Adhimantha* through the combination of systemic and local therapies. Therapies include *Tarpana*, *Ashchyotana*, *Nasya*, *Anjana* along with herbal formulations which improves ocular health. *Chandrakala Rasa* and *Mauktika Kamadugha* are examples of internal medications that have *Pitta-Shamana* and *Raktaprasadana* properties, which will help to reduce retinal hemorrhages and vascular lesions. *Chakshushya Dravyas* such as *Amalaki*, *Haritaki*, *Tulsi* and *Guduchi*, etc. contain antioxidants, anti-inflammatories and rejuvenators that support eye health.^[4,5]

Nasya Karma can be used to alleviate any impact of disease on *Urhwahajatrugata Vyadhis* using medicated preparation such as *Vasa Ghrita*. Topical applications such as *Raktachandanadi Bidalaka*, along with herbs included, *Nimba*, *Patola*, *Yashtimadhu*, *Guduchi*, and *Vasa*, that can help to calm *Pitta* and *Rakta* through their *Tikta* and *Kashaya* properties as well as their *Shophahara* effects. Ayurvedic treatment for this condition involves correcting the imbalance of the *Dosha* and restoring regular circulation to the body. Ways in

which this can be achieved include *Snehana* followed by *Virechan*, with the use of herbal formulations such as *Trivrutta Leha* to decrease *Pitta Dosha*, which is associated with conditions such as retinopathy.^[7-9]

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda considers *Netra* health is of prime concern since it play vital role in human life. Ayurveda categorizes the many reasons for eye disorders into categories of *Nidana*, which contain all possible causes of eye problems, including diet, lifestyle, mental state, environment, and trauma. An important aspect of the eye is vascular health (*Sira Nidana*) in order to have healthy eyes; affectations of this area could lead to a number of problems in the eyes, e.g., ischemia, hemorrhage and inflammation etc. Eye problems arise from an imbalance of the *Dosha* and blockage of *Srotas* related to *Raktavaha srotas* and *Alochaka pitta*. Ayurveda focuses not only on relieving symptoms, but also on correcting any underlying imbalance through prevention, detoxification, and rejuvenation. To achieve effective maintenance and restoration of eye health, a combination of *Nidana parivarjana*, systemic cleansing and local ocular treatment is necessary. *Shodhana* and *Rasayana* therapies help to prevent and treat ocular disorders. Ayurveda *Kriyakalpa* treatments (*Tarpana*, *Ashchyotana* and *Anjana*) are effective ways to treat dry eye syndrome, conjunctivitis, glaucoma, and refractive errors.

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